

1 Unveiling clutch investment strategies in birds: A case
2 study on great tits using generalized additive models

3 Socias-Martínez, Lluís¹, Álvarez, Elena², Louise R., Peckre³ and Barba, Emilio²

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5 ¹Department of Sciences and Technology, Institut National Universitaire Jean-François
6 Champollion, The University of Toulouse, Albi, France

7 ²“Cavanilles” Institute of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology, University of Valencia, Valencia,
8 Spain

9 ³Laboratoire d'Ethologie Expérimentale et Comparée UR 4443 (LEEC), Université Sorbonne Paris
10 Nord, F-93430 Villetaneuse, France

11

12 *Corresponding author: luissociasm@gmail.com

13 Lluís Socias-Martínez: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1739-0987>

14 Elena Álvarez: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8256-443X>

15 Louise Peckre: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0065-8529>

16 Emilio Barba: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2882-9788>

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18 Acknowledgments

19 We thank two anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments on the first version of this article.
20 Part of the data collection was funded by projects PS90-0266 (Spanish Ministry of Education and
21 Science) and GV-2517/94 (Generalitat Valenciana). Analyses and writing have been funded by
22 project PID2021-122171NB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ (Ministry of Science and
23 Innovation and FEDER, UE). We thank the Spanish Meteorological Agency (AEMET) for providing
24 temperature data from our study site. We thank David March Morlà for making this collaboration
25 possible. We also thank Raquel Monclús for kindly answering our questions.

26 Conflict of interest

27 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

28 Author contributions

29 EB conceived the ideas and collected the data; EB and LS-M designed the methodology; EÁ and
30 EB curated and rendered the data available for analyses; LS-M and LP analyzed the data; LS-M
31 and EB led the writing of the manuscript. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave
32 final approval for publication. All authors approve the publication of this work. All authors agree
33 to be accountable for the aspects of the work that they conducted and to ensure that the accuracy
34 and integrity of any part of their work to be appropriately investigated and resolved.

35 Our study includes authors based in various countries and from several nationalities. Half of the
36 authors are long-term based in the locality where the data was collected and regularly publish in
37 the local language. Through this collaboration, correct interpretation of data and inclusion of
38 several perspectives were ensured.

39 **Data availability statement**

40 The data and R scripts used in this preprint are available at Zenodo with accompanying metadata:

41 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15161123>.

42 Abstract

43 Reproductive effort involves trade-offs among offspring and with homeostasis. In birds, a crucial
44 parental investment concerns the allocation of resources to each egg. Variation in egg investment
45 has led to the development of hypotheses regarding whether females favor the eldest nestlings
46 (“brood reduction”) or distribute resources more evenly (“brood survival”). Alternative
47 explanations include the maturation of reproductive organs and trade-offs with environmental
48 constraints, such as thermoregulation. The earliest tests of these hypotheses relied on the
49 deviation of the last egg’s volume from the clutch mean (D). More recent studies have often
50 overlooked non-linearity and temporal autocorrelation in egg investments. Here, we analyze 145
51 broods comprising 1,084 eggs from a great tit (*Parus major*) population in eastern Spain using
52 generalized additive mixed-effects models (GAMMs). Laying order influenced egg volume, with
53 most variation occurring as an increase from the first to middle eggs in the clutch, followed by a
54 slight decrease. We favor the interpretation that females adopt a brood survival strategy because:
55 (1) volume changes were of small magnitude (approx. 5%); (2) no significant negative effects of
56 the number of eggs developing simultaneously in the ovary, total clutch size, or minimum
57 temperatures were found; and (3) the laying order effect prevailed throughout the breeding
58 season. However, within this brood survival strategy, females slightly favored middle eggs. In
59 addition, negative correlations among deviations in volume from the main strategy suggest that
60 energetic trade-offs were present. Finally, most variation occurred between clutches, reinforcing
61 previous findings of limited plasticity in egg volume in birds. Our results further caution against
62 relying on mean egg volume (D) as a measure of investment strategies and highlight the
63 importance of considering non-linearity and temporal autocorrelation in analyses of reproductive
64 investment. The use of GAMMs provides a robust approach to overcoming previous analytical
65 limitations in the study of within-clutch variation in egg investment.

66

67 **Keywords:** Brood reduction strategy, Brood survival strategy, Egg laying order, Egg volume, Non-
68 linear modeling, *Parus major*, Reproductive strategy, Temporal autocorrelation.

69

70 Introduction

71 Life-history theory predicts that reproductive investments will be traded off against other
72 energetic expenditures (Stearns 1992). One of the most salient expectations arising from
73 investment trade-offs is the negative relationship between offspring number and quality (Clutton-
74 Brock 1991; Stearns 1992; Royle et al. 2012). This negative correlation has been observed across
75 taxa (Fleming and Gross 1990; Blackburn 1991; Christians 2000; Williams 2001; Charnov and
76 Ernest 2006; Song et al. 2020). In addition, trade-offs in energetic or temporal investments occur
77 both between and within breeding attempts. Parents might be selected to adopt reproductive
78 strategies that maximize lifetime reproductive success by adjusting investment in different broods
79 or offspring depending on expected payoffs. Consequently, investment in offspring number,
80 quality, and sex should be conditional on internal and external factors, as well as on future
81 reproductive opportunities within the same or subsequent breeding periods (Trivers and Willard
82 1973; Slagsvold et al. 1984; Stearns 1992).

83 Egg volume has been linked to offspring survival and fecundity in birds (Slagsvold et al. 1984;
84 Williams 1994; Krist 2011), making it a key component of maternal investment. As predicted by
85 life-history theory, clutch size tends to be negatively correlated with egg size across avian species
86 (Blackburn 1991; Christians 2000; Williams 2001; Song et al. 2020). Within bird populations, most
87 variation in egg volume is explained by female identity, and egg size is highly repeatable and
88 heritable compared to other reproductive traits (Christians 2002). Thus, egg volume has been
89 suggested to be relatively fixed around an optimal value, with the number of offspring per brood
90 and the timing of laying being the primary variables for adjustment in response to internal (e.g.,
91 body condition) and external (e.g., temperature) variation (Christians 2002). Despite this
92 proposed stability, evidence suggests that females adjust egg volume within clutches. You et al.
93 (2009) identified three main patterns of egg volume variation as a function of laying order: an
94 increase, a decrease, or an increase followed by a decrease.

95 Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain these patterns based on maternal
96 manipulation of offspring survival and competitiveness through variation in egg size. The
97 increasing pattern is thought to reflect a strategy that maximizes the survival of each offspring in
98 the face of asynchronous hatching (the “brood survival hypothesis” (Clark and Wilson 1981)
99 Slagsvold et al. 1984). In this case, mothers compensate for the development disadvantages of
100 later-hatched chicks by increasing egg size (Howe 1976). The second pattern, a decrease in egg
101 size as a function of laying order, has been associated with a differential investment strategy
102 favoring earlier offspring (the “brood reduction hypothesis”, Edwards and Collopy 1983; Viñuela
103 1997). This strategy is thought to be associated with producing more offspring than the
104 environment can support, with surplus offspring being smaller and only successfully reared under
105 particularly favorable conditions. The third pattern, an increase followed by a decrease, could
106 reflect a mixed strategy, where females initially follow a “brood survival” strategy but later produce
107 smaller, less costly eggs in anticipation of variable environmental conditions. Additionally, some
108 species may switch between these strategies depending on external or internal factors (e.g.,
109 Christensen and Balsby 2020).

110 Alternative hypotheses suggest that variation in egg volume is primarily driven by female condition
111 at the time of egg production. According to such hypotheses, if females had equal investment
112 capacities throughout laying, we would expect a constant mean egg volume with random
113 variation. However, constraints on female physiology may lead to systematic variation. First,
114 reproductive organs may not maintain consistent efficiency, resulting in changes in egg volume
115 as laying progresses (Parsons 1976). For instance, if ovarian maturation is not complete at the
116 beginning of egg laying, egg volume might increase with laying order as a direct consequence of
117 improving ovarian efficiency. Second, egg volume may be influenced by fluctuations in female
118 energy levels (Järvinen and Ylimaunu 1986; Wiebe and Bortolotti 1996). In highly seasonal
119 environments, the first eggs may be produced under conditions of food scarcity and/or low
120 temperatures that increase thermoregulatory costs, leading to a subsequent increase in egg

121 volume as conditions improve. Both effects could produce an increase in egg volume without
122 needing to invoke a “brood survival” strategy. Conversely, if investment in earlier eggs depletes
123 maternal energy reserves, a carryover effect could cause a decline in egg volume with laying order
124 without the need to appeal to a “brood reduction” strategy. The third pattern of increase and
125 decrease could likewise occur by a combination of the above-mentioned effects arising from
126 female condition.

127 Previous studies examining clutch investment strategies in birds have suffered from three
128 limitations: they 1) relied on diverse forms of data simplification, 2) ignored temporal
129 autocorrelation, and 3) did not test systematically for competing hypotheses. Regarding 1), the
130 broadest and most cited comparative study to date on egg size variation as a function of laying
131 order focuses on a single egg. Slagsvold et al. (1984) analyzed the deviation of the final egg relative
132 to the mean clutch volume (denoted as D) across various avian orders as a function of several life
133 history and ecological variables. The authors justified their choice because they found that the
134 overall level of change between one egg and the next was highly correlated to D in the Hooded
135 Crow ($r = 0.55$, $N_{\text{clutch}} = 16$). Despite the advantages of such simple and broadly applicable
136 measure, D accurately describes investment strategies whenever the last egg is the only one to
137 consistently deviate from the mean or when the progression in egg volume is monotonic and/or
138 linear. Recent studies using the entire clutch, however, suggest that variation in egg volume arises
139 through deviations in all eggs in a non-linear way (Tab. 1). These studies have dealt with non-
140 linearity by using quadratic terms or transforming egg position into a factor within linear mixed
141 models or ANOVAs. Regarding 2), while some of the recent studies consider all eggs in a clutch
142 using linear mixed-effects models, a method that can explicitly consider investment dependence
143 across eggs within clutches using time series has not yet been applied (Tab.1). Regarding 3), most
144 studies did not aim at testing the brood reduction or survival hypotheses nor alternative
145 hypotheses based on female condition. Because of this, other sources of variation in egg volume,
146 such as trade-offs with thermoregulation, have yet to be tested (Tab. 1). New studies could benefit

147 from using a multivariate non-linear modeling framework accounting for temporal
148 autocorrelation.

149 The use of hierarchical generalized additive mixed-effects models (GAMMs hereafter, Wood 2017;
150 Pedersen et al. 2019) could prove useful in this context. GAMMs can model complex non-linear
151 functions without constraining their shape before model fitting and can incorporate multivariate
152 effects and sources of dependence, such as random effects. We take advantage of GAMMs to
153 explore clutch investment strategies in light of existing hypotheses in a great tit (*Parus major*)
154 population from south-eastern Spain. Previous studies investigating egg variation in relation to
155 laying order in *Parus major* found a multitude of relationships, perhaps suffering from small
156 sample sizes and the three methodological limitations reviewed in the previous paragraph (Tab.
157 1). Given the taxonomic variation in patterns of egg volume across the laying order, the observed
158 within-species diversity, and the limitations found, our study can contribute both valuable data
159 for future comparative analyses of this biological phenomenon and a new methodological
160 approach.

161 Specifically, we test for variation in egg volume arising from: 1) an effect of laying order, and we
162 predict an increase in egg volume if females use a brood survival strategy or undergo a maturation
163 of ovarian tissue during laying, a decrease if they follow instead a brood reduction strategy or there
164 is a carryover of costs of egg production during egg laying, or a non-linear change if females follow
165 a mixed strategy or suffer from maturation and carryover effects; 2) a changing effect of laying
166 order depending on clutch size, and we predict that as clutch size increases, last eggs become
167 relatively smaller if females follow a brood reduction or suffer from increased costs when under
168 conditions of high competition within clutches; 3) a negative effect of temperature on egg volume,
169 and we predict that as temperatures lower, egg size decreases if female reproductive investment
170 is traded off against thermoregulation; 4) a dependence of investments in egg volume between
171 consecutive eggs, and predict that after accounting for main strategies of egg volume as a

172 function of laying order, autocorrelation should be negative if egg volume investments are traded
173 off against each other.

174 Materials and methods

175 *Study population and measures*

176 The great tit (*Parus major*) is a small passerine bird from the family Paridae, with an average mass
177 of 17–19 g and a wingspan of 22–25 cm in Spanish populations (Atiénzar et al. 2016). Our study
178 population was in Sagunto, Valencia (eastern Spain, 39°42'N, 0°15'W, 30 m a.s.l.), within an area
179 dominated by orange monoculture. The population has been monitored since 1986 using artificial
180 nest boxes (Álvarez and Barba 2014; Solís et al. 2021), but individual identification of adult birds
181 was not available in the early years when the data of the present study was collected (1988, 1990,
182 1992, 1993, and 1994). Great tits typically lay one egg per day during the laying period until the
183 clutch is complete. Each egg develops in the oviduct for three days before being laid shortly after
184 sunrise on the fourth day (Song et al. 2020). In this population, females may produce up to two
185 broods per year, although most laid only one during the years of this study (Solís et al. 2021).
186 During the years when the data used in this study was collected, clutch size was 7.68 ± 0.67 (mean
187 \pm std. deviation, $N_{\text{years}} = 5$).

188 For this study, a subset of randomly selected nests was checked daily from the beginning of nest
189 construction during each breeding season. Once egg laying began, each egg was individually
190 marked with a consecutive number using a permanent felt pen. When the clutch was completed
191 (no new eggs were found for two consecutive days), the length and breadth of each egg were
192 measured with a caliper. All measurements were taken by the same observer (EB) using the same
193 caliper across the five study years to ensure consistency.

194 Egg volume was estimated using the formula: $v = 0.4673LB^2 + 0.042$, where L is the length, B is
195 the breadth, and the constants were specifically estimated for great tits (Ojanen et al. 1978). Egg

196 sphericity was calculated as a ratio between width and length (width/length; Hůrak et al. 1995).
197 During the study period, some pairs laid a second clutch (after a successful first one) or a
198 replacement clutch (after failure). As it is standard in these studies (e.g., Van Noordwijk et al.
199 1995; Solís et al. 2023), we considered first clutches those started within the 30 days following
200 the start of the first clutch each year, classifying the rest as “late” clutches, which might include
201 both replacement and second clutches. In total, 1,084 eggs from 145 different clutches were
202 measured over the five breeding seasons.

203 As, by the time of egg laying, low temperatures are expected to act as a constraint, minimum
204 temperatures for the three days preceding each egg’s laying date (i.e., the period of egg formation)
205 were obtained from a nearby (c.a. 3 Km) meteorological station operated by the Spanish
206 Meteorological Agency (AEMET).

207 The authorization to carry out this work was implicit in the project grant that funded it. No
208 additional permission was required to carry out this work.

209 *Statistics*

210 All analyses were performed using R software (version 4.4.0, R Core Team 2024). A complete list
211 of the packages used can be found in the supplementary information (SI hereafter).

212 We modeled variation in egg volume as a function of multiple covariates of interest. Because
213 using a standard equation derived for great tits might conflate possible changes in different egg
214 dimensions responsible for modifications in egg volume, we investigated three additional
215 morphological measures: egg width, length, and sphericity in supplementary analyses. Since
216 clutch identity accounted for most of the variation in egg volume, we further explored, in a
217 supplementary analysis, predictors of differences between clutches in mean egg volume. We
218 used hierarchical generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs) implemented in the *mgcv* R
219 package (Wood 2017; Pedersen et al. 2019). This flexible modeling framework allowed us to

220 account for non-linearity in preliminary graphic assessments of the relationships between
221 variables. Additionally, GAMMs can incorporate non-linear temporal autocorrelation when time is
222 included as a covariate (Simpson 2018), which is relevant in the context of sequential egg-laying.
223 We modeled the data using a Gaussian distribution with an identity link function. The models were
224 fitted using fast restricted maximum likelihood (fREML), as this method has been shown to
225 provide more robust estimates of the optimal penalization for the wiggleness of smooth functions
226 compared to other available approaches (Wood 2017). To ensure model adequacy, we evaluated
227 the number of basis dimensions, checked for concurvity (i.e., generalized form of collinearity)
228 between smooth functions, and assessed the contribution of each variable to deviance and
229 variance explained using standard GAM diagnostic procedures. Because variation between
230 clutches is secondary to the main interest of this article, we provide a further description of these
231 analyses and their results in the SI. The data and R code used in these analyses are available at
232 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15161123>.

233 *Within clutches: Egg model*

234 The response variable, egg volume, was standard scored (scaled hereafter) based on the entire
235 dataset ($n_{\text{egg}} = 1,084$). Transformation and modeling of egg width, length, and sphericity were
236 equivalent to those carried out for egg volume and can be found in the supplementary information
237 (SI Supplementary within-clutch models: Analyzing changes in egg width, length, and sphericity).

238 Main effects

239 Smooth functions of three covariates were included using cubic regression splines: First, egg
240 position in the laying sequence was incorporated to assess potential differences in volume
241 investment, as predicted in the “brood survival” and “brood reduction” hypotheses (Slagsvold et
242 al. 1984), maturation of ovary or carryover costs of egg production (Parsons 1976). Second, clutch
243 size was included as a proxy for overall reproductive investment, which is expected to be
244 negatively correlated with egg volume (Blackburn 1991; Christians 2000; Williams 2001; Song et
245 al. 2020). Third, the mean minimum temperature during the three days of egg formation was

246 considered, given that lower temperatures may increase energetic demands for
247 thermoregulation, potentially reducing egg volume (Järvinen and Ylimaunu 1986).

248 The egg position in the laying sequence was scaled within each clutch using standard scoring,
249 while the other two independent variables were scaled across the entire dataset. Pearson
250 correlation coefficients were used to assess collinearity among variables, and highly correlated
251 variables were excluded to prevent concavity in the model. As a result, egg laying date was not
252 included in the models, despite its potential effect on investment strategies, due to its strong
253 negative correlation with minimum temperature (see Supplementary Information, hereafter SI).

254 Interactions

255 Additionally, we included two interactions. The interactions between egg-laying order and clutch
256 size and minimum temperature and clutch size were modeled as isotropic bivariate smooths
257 using thin plate splines. Isotropic smooths were chosen because all interacting variables were
258 scaled, meaning they shared the same unit of measurement (standard deviations) (Wood 2017).
259 First, the interaction between egg laying order and the clutch size was included, as investment
260 strategies have been observed to vary depending on clutch size (Christensen and Balsby 2020).
261 Second, an interaction between minimum temperature and clutch size was incorporated to
262 account for differences in competitive pressure during egg formation. Since each egg develops in
263 the oviduct for three days, a given position in the laying order does not imply the same competition
264 in all clutches. For example, the fourth egg develops alongside four other eggs in a clutch of six
265 but only two in a clutch of four. This difference in competition could influence how resources are
266 allocated, and temperature effects may differ depending on the overall intensity of competition
267 within the clutch, justifying the inclusion of this interaction.

268 Random intercepts and slopes

269 We included two random intercepts: year and clutch identity. The inclusion of the year was
270 justified by visual inspection, which revealed variation in clutch size and mean egg volume across

271 years, suggesting potential dependency driven by fluctuations in resource availability due to
272 changes in rainfall or other abiotic and biotic factors (see SI Explored features). Since egg volume
273 was scaled using the entire dataset, including clutch identity as a random intercept allowed us to
274 estimate the variation attributable to female identity, which serves as a proxy given that individual
275 identification was unavailable for the early years of this long-term study. Additionally, accounting
276 for clutch identity helped control for the dependence inherent in data collected within the same
277 clutch.

278 We also considered incorporating a factor smooth interaction (analogous to a random slope) to
279 model the effect of egg position in the laying sequence for each clutch. This approach aimed to
280 capture potential variation in laying strategies among females, as suggested by preliminary data
281 visualizations. However, including this random slope led to non-normality in residuals and high
282 concavity (SI, Diagnostics). Given that the full model, without this term, did not exhibit such
283 violations, we opted for its exclusion in the final analysis (see Results).

284 Temporal autocorrelation

285 To account for the dependence in the egg-laying process, understood as a time series, we
286 incorporated an autocorrelation structure in the model residuals. Since the *mgcv* package
287 requires specifying the rank of the first-order autocorrelation process, we first ran the full egg
288 model both with and without random slopes, assessing the presence of autocorrelation in their
289 residuals. To do this, we correlated the residuals of each model with a lagged version, excluding
290 matches from different clutches. In both cases, we detected moderate but significant
291 autocorrelation, albeit with opposite signs (full model without random slopes: Pearson coefficient
292 = 0.19, $t = 5.92$, $df = 932$, $p < 0.001$; full model with random slopes: Pearson coefficient = -0.24, t
293 = -7.57, $df = 932$, $p < 0.001$). We re-ran both models, this time incorporating the autocorrelation
294 structure corresponding to each case. For partial models analyzing the contribution of each
295 variable, we used the autocorrelation level of the full model without random slopes, as these
296 models did not include the random slopes.

297 Model diagnostics

298 The model appeared correctly specified regarding k-basis dimensions, considering the reduction
299 in degrees of freedom after penalization and the k-indexes (SI, Diagnostics). No violations of
300 normality of residuals or homoskedasticity were detected. Observed concurvity was generally low
301 and arose mainly from random factors. It exceeded 50% in only two cases (SI Concurvity). The first
302 involved the random intercept of clutch identity and minimum temperature (concurvity = 0.82),
303 indicating that different clutches were exposed to distinct temperature ranges as the season
304 progressed. The second involved the smooth function of clutch size and its interaction with
305 minimum temperature (concurvity = 51%). Overall, the GAMM model met the necessary
306 assumptions for investigating the effects of explanatory variables.

307 *Dependence between investments*

308 As a further step in the analysis, we examined whether the raw residuals from the full egg GAMM
309 exhibited any systematic pattern. Specifically, we tested whether, beyond the strategy employed
310 by each female regarding egg volume as a function of laying order, investments in individual eggs
311 were influenced by investments in other eggs within the same clutch. This two-step approach can
312 be understood as follows: while the previous model captured the non-linear trend in investment
313 over the laying sequence within each clutch, this step evaluated whether deviations from that
314 trend exhibit internal dependencies. To investigate this, we computed both autocorrelation (ACF)
315 and partial autocorrelation (PACF) of the residuals for each clutch using the `acf()` and `pacf()`
316 functions in R. The `acf()` function estimated the correlation between each value in a series and its
317 lagged values. The `pacf()` function, in turn, fits an autoregressive model, where each value in the
318 series is modeled as a function of its past values, with coefficients estimated by minimizing
319 squared errors (Shumway and Stoffer 2017). To determine statistical significance of the observed
320 values, we calculated the non-significant interval for a white-noise series using the equation $\pm \frac{2}{\sqrt{\bar{n}}}$,
321 where \bar{n} represents the mean clutch size. Given that these methods are typically applied to large
322 time-series datasets, whereas our dataset consists of multiple short series, we also computed

323 the mean \pm standard deviation of the autocorrelation coefficients for each lag. Finally, we
324 assessed the significance of the results by examining whether this interval overlapped with zero.

325

326 Results

327 The egg full model explained 81.1% of the deviance observed in the null model. Females differed

328 in their mean egg volume (mean = 1,506.24 mm³, coefficient of variation = 7.69%), and as a

Figure 1 | Egg volume as a function of laying order: The x axis shows the position in the egg laying order of a given egg scaled per clutch size, y axis on the left shows the egg volume in mm³ while the y axis on the right represents egg volumes as deviation in percentage from the mean egg volume. The points show values observed and grey lines connect values from eggs in the same brood. The red line indicates the mean egg volume observed. The black line indicates the predicted values by the GAMM model excluding effects of other variables with the 95% confidence interval in shaded blue.

329 consequence, the random intercept per clutch accounted for the largest portion of deviance
330 explained, 78.2% ($F = 19.2$, $p < 0.001$). All terms including egg position, as a main effect and as an
331 interaction, contributed 2.88% (main effect $F = 3.83$, $p < 0.001$; SI Deviance and significance
332 smooths), while the interaction between minimum temperature and egg position in the laying
333 order contributed 0.37% ($F = 17.26$, $p = 0.076$). Other variables did not significantly contribute to
334 the explanatory power of the model. Additionally, the calculation of variance components
335 supported these findings regarding the partial effects of each variable (SI Variance).

336 After accounting for inter-female variation, first-laid eggs tended to be slightly smaller than the
337 clutch mean, followed by a gradual increase in size, peaking towards the middle of the laying
338 sequence and then decreasing again, with the last eggs returning to the clutch mean (see Fig. 1).
339 This laying order effect was relatively small, with deviations ranging between circa -2.5% and +2%
340 from mean egg volume. Additionally, supplementary analyses indicate that the non-linear
341 increase in egg volume as a function of laying order appears to be mediated by a saturating
342 increase in egg width (-2% to +0.75% of width mean; see SI Effects covariates) concurrent with a
343 less pronounced two-step decrease in egg length (+0.5% to -0.5% of length mean, see SI Main
344 effects). These changes in egg width and length resulted in a non-linear increase in egg sphericity
345 as laying order progressed (-2.5% to +1.75% of sphericity mean; see SI Effects covariates). Thus,
346 eggs became wider, shorter, more spherical, and more voluminous as the laying order progressed.

347 Minimum ambient temperature during the formation did not significantly affect egg volume (SI
348 Effects covariates and Significance tests). However, the interaction between egg position and
349 temperature showed a non-significant trend, suggesting that temperature changes could
350 influence egg volume differently depending on laying order ($F = 17.26$, $p = 0.076$, Fig. 2), albeit of
351 limited effect size, circa -2.5% and +2% from mean egg volume. While middle eggs remained
352 relatively stable, first-laid eggs were smaller at higher temperatures. In contrast, later-laid eggs
353 were smaller at lower temperatures, though the magnitude of this effect was weaker than the
354 observed for first-laid eggs.

Figure 2 | Egg volume as a function of laying order and minimum temperature: The x axis shows the position in the egg laying order of a given egg scaled per brood size, y axis shows the temperature in °C and the z axis on the left shows the egg volume in mm³. The black points show values observed. The 3D surface depicts the predicted values based on the egg full model without random slopes. Bluer colors indicate smaller and yellower bigger eggs.

355 Clutch size did not significantly affect egg volume either as a main effect or through interactions
 356 (SI Effects covariates and Significance tests). There was a non-significant trend of limited effect
 357 size indicating that larger clutches contained slightly larger eggs (circa -2.5% and +2% mean
 358 volume), with the notable exception of a single four-egg clutch, which had a mean egg volume
 359 higher than all others (SI Effects covariates). Interannual differences in egg volume were limited
 360 and not significant (SI Effects covariates and Significance tests).

361 The standardized residuals of the models did not exhibit significant within-clutch correlations
 362 when compared to a white noise series of similar size (Fig. 3). All mean correlations per lag
 363 between two observations fell within the non-significant range. However, when analyzing lags
 364 within and between raw and standardized residuals, certain patterns emerged. The
 365 autocorrelation structure implemented in the model effectively reduced the mean correlation for
 366 lag one to zero (Fig 3, SI Autocorrelation). Moreover, while autocorrelation between raw residuals
 367 of eggs laid one day apart was generally positive (SI Autocorrelation), the correlation between eggs

368 further apart in the laying sequence tended to shift towards negative values. Thus, investments
369 beyond or below the predicted strategy seemed to occur in pairs of eggs and might have entailed

Figure 3 | Autocorrelation coefficients for standardized residuals in the egg full model without random slopes: The x axis represents the lag in days within a clutch between two residuals of egg volume. The y-axes indicate the Pearson correlation coefficient or the coefficient from autoregressive models. Points represent calculated values for individual clutches, while blue triangles show the mean correlation for each lag with standard deviations represented by error bars. The upper panel displays autocorrelation values, and the lower panel shows partial autocorrelation functions. Black lines mark a correlation of 0, while blue lines delineate the non-significant range, which accounts for expected values under a white noise series with a sample size equivalent to the mean clutch size.

370 competition with eggs coming later in the laying order.

371 Discussion

372 Changes in egg volume within clutches have been explained either as an adaptive manipulation
373 of offspring phenotypes or as a by-product of females' physiological regulation. We found
374 evidence for consistent patterns in egg volume variation according to laying order in this great tit
375 population, albeit of small magnitude (approximately 5% of the mean egg volume). Our results
376 show that the first eggs in the clutch were slightly smaller than average, whereas middle and later

377 eggs tended to be slightly larger. Neither the minimum temperatures during egg formation nor
378 clutch size significantly predicted egg volume or differences in mean egg volume between
379 clutches (see SI), although some trends were observed. Finally, most of the variation in egg
380 volume was explained by clutch identity. We discuss the adaptive, by-product, and
381 methodological implications of our results in the next sections.

382 *Variation in egg volume as a tool for strategic offspring prioritization?*

383 In a meta-analysis, Krist (2011) shows that, across bird species, egg size is strongly correlated
384 with fitness proxies such as hatchling mass and condition (circa 0.8 and 0.6, respectively; see Fig.
385 4 in Krist 2011). Moreover, egg size is consistently associated with later body mass (circa 0.3 from
386 nestling to post-fledging stages) and survival (circa 0.2 for both nestling and post-fledging).
387 According to the adaptive manipulation set of hypotheses regarding within-clutch variation in
388 investment, some species aim to enhance the survival of the entire brood (the “brood survival”
389 hypothesis), while others prioritize larger chicks at the expense of smaller ones (the “brood
390 reduction” hypothesis; Slagsvold et al. 1984). Thus, variation in egg volume appears to be a key
391 maternal mechanism that can be adaptively adjusted throughout the laying sequence.

392 In this study, we found that egg volume tends to increase as laying progresses. However, we also
393 observed a slight decrease in volume between the middle and last eggs, suggesting that females
394 prioritize the middle eggs, invest secondarily in the last ones, and allocate the least investment to
395 the first. In approximately 63% of clutches in the study population, females begin incubation after
396 completing the clutch (Álvarez and Barba 2014). Combined with the increasing egg volume
397 pattern observed here, this suggests that in synchronously incubated clutches, females may be
398 favoring middle and late eggs over the first-laid ones. In the remaining 37% of clutches, incubation
399 begins before clutch completion, typically with 76% of these cases starting when the penultimate
400 egg is laid (Álvarez and Barba 2014). In such asynchronous clutches, middle eggs still enjoy an
401 advantage over the first ones, being larger and hatching at the same time. Meanwhile, although
402 the last egg hatches later, its larger size might compensate for the delay, potentially placing it on

403 a more equal footing with earlier hatchlings. If this pattern holds, females may be employing a
404 mild form of brood reduction – not in the conventional sense of disadvantaging the last eggs, but
405 rather by disadvantaging the first.

406 In blue tits (*Parus caeruleus*), Nilsson and Svensson (1993) found that the first egg was generally
407 smaller and that in asynchronously incubated nests, the last egg was significantly larger
408 compared to synchronously incubated ones. Thus, the shape of the egg volume investment
409 pattern observed in the present study might have been influenced by the females' incubation
410 strategies. Further research measuring incubation behaviour alongside egg size throughout the
411 laying period in great tits is needed.

412 Although the observed changes in egg volume are relatively small (circa 5%), our results suggest
413 that, overall, females follow a brood survival strategy while slightly favoring middle eggs – though
414 not to the extent that clearly supports a brood reduction scenario. Additionally, due to the modest
415 effect size of laying order on egg volume, the significance of this variation for long-term fitness
416 outcomes remains uncertain. While survival and body condition correlate with egg volume,
417 implying potential effects on lifetime reproductive success, interpretations should be made
418 cautiously. First, Krist (2011) used Pearson's correlation coefficient as an effect size measure,
419 which reflects the signal-to-noise ratio rather than the magnitude of biological impact. Second,
420 studies in tits suggest that although egg size influences hatchling mass and early growth, these
421 differences often diminish as nestlings age (Schifferli 1973; Nilsson and Svensson 1993; You et al.
422 2009). Further studies on the fitness consequences of egg volume and laying order in great tits
423 and other species are necessary to determine the biological relevance of these findings.

424 In altricial species, parents can further adjust post-hatching care to either reinforce or
425 compensate for initial differences among chicks, affecting survival and reproductive potential. It
426 is, therefore, important to consider post-hatching parental investment when interpreting
427 reproductive strategies related to within-clutch resource allocation. For example, You et al. (2009)

428 found that in a Chinese great tit population, therefore mitigating size disadvantages. Conversely,
429 in a Korean population, Kang and Lee (2023) found no evidence of selective feeding based on
430 laying order. More research is needed to determine whether the relationship between laying order
431 and egg volume is shaped by both pre- and post-hatching investment and to clarify which
432 hypothesis – brood survival or brood reduction – is better supported.

433 *Beyond adaptation: Energetic costs and reproductive organ maturation?*

434 The next set of hypotheses explains variation in egg volume as a by-product of the female's
435 changing capacity to invest in egg formation during the laying process. According to these
436 hypotheses, the pattern observed in our results – an initial increase in egg volume followed by a
437 slight decrease – does not necessarily imply that females prioritize middle offspring. Instead, it
438 may result from a combination of reproductive organ maturation and the energetic costs
439 associated with egg production (Parsons 1976; Järvinen and Ylimaunu 1986; Wiebe and Bortolotti
440 1996). As reproductive organs mature, egg volume is expected to increase over the course of
441 laying. However, if females progressively deplete their energetic reserves, the volume of later eggs
442 may be reduced. Thus, the observed pattern could reflect these two processes – maturation and
443 increasing energetic costs – acting simultaneously throughout the laying sequence.

444 Although we lack direct data on reproductive organ maturation, we observed consistent increases
445 in egg volume with laying order across clutches throughout the season (SI Explored features). This
446 observation suggests that even “late” clutches (See Study population and measures), for which
447 reproductive maturation of reproductive organs should already be complete at the onset of laying,
448 exhibited the same volume pattern. Therefore, it is unlikely that the observed effects of laying
449 order are driven by seasonal reproductive maturation. Nonetheless, the concurrent changes we
450 observed in egg width and length may indicate short-term maturation processes operating within
451 individual clutches, potentially enabling the production of wider eggs as laying progresses (SI
452 Supplementary within-clutch models).

453 Our results provide mixed evidence regarding the role of energetic trade-offs in shaping egg
454 volume. First, middle eggs often develop concurrently with a greater number of other eggs and
455 over the full laying period – particularly in larger clutches. Despite this, middle eggs tended to be
456 the largest, and we found no effect of clutch size on this pattern. Supporting the idea that
457 energetic trade-offs during egg formation may not be the primary driver, we found no significant
458 effect of minimum ambient temperatures, which would be expected to reflect competing
459 demands between thermoregulation and egg production. Interestingly, we did find a trend for
460 larger first eggs under lower temperatures, suggesting that females may compensate for more
461 challenging conditions by investing more in early eggs. Since temperature did not predict mean
462 clutch volume (see SI Clutch model), this pattern may reflect an effort to reduce the disadvantage
463 of first-laid eggs, further supporting a brood survival strategy.

464 Given that our study population is located in the Mediterranean region, ambient temperatures
465 experienced during laying are generally warmer than in the populations examined in earlier
466 studies (e.g., Järvinen and Ylimaunu 1986). These authors found that, in the Pied Flycatcher, the
467 deviation of the last egg from the mean egg volume (D) was negative when temperatures were
468 below 6 °C and positive at higher temperatures, with greater differences under higher temperature
469 variability. If we had used D , our results would align with their findings: later eggs tended to be
470 larger, and first eggs had lower mean volumes in warmer conditions. While the D metric supports
471 the idea of changes driven by energetic constraints, the investment in first eggs under cold
472 conditions suggests that this explanation is incomplete.

473 At the same time, we found some indication that energetic trade-offs among eggs may influence
474 volume allocation. Residuals from the full model suggest that when females invest heavily in a
475 specific egg, the volume of subsequent eggs – except for the one laid immediately after – tends to
476 be reduced. A similar trade-off has been described in blue tits, where females produced smaller
477 first eggs unless supplemented with food (Nilsson and Svensson 1993). Considering the evidence
478 from both adaptive manipulation and by-product hypotheses, we suggest that female great tits in

479 eastern Spain adopt a brood survival strategy while slightly favoring middle eggs, particularly
480 under more favorable environmental conditions.

481 To further disentangle the mechanisms behind the observed pattern, future studies should
482 experimentally manipulate resource availability during laying. Such approaches could clarify
483 whether egg volume allocation arises from strategic investments under energetic constraints or
484 from physiological limitations imposed by reproductive organ maturation at the start of the clutch.

485 *Limits of traditional metrics and the promise of new analytical tools*

486 Interpreting our results in the context of previous studies on *Parus major* is challenging due to
487 differences in metrics, sample sizes, and statistical approaches (Tab. 1). The only study that
488 allows for a clear point of comparison – due to its focus on egg volume and a comparable sample
489 size – is that of You et al. (2009). Their clutch size range (6-14 eggs) was broader than ours (4-10
490 eggs), and they modeled the relationship linearly. However, their results also suggest a non-linear
491 pattern within the overall increase detected. In their Figure 2, egg volume appears to increase and
492 then slightly decline, with a slightly larger magnitude than in our population (5-10% vs. 5% of mean
493 egg volume). Given that other studies had much smaller sample sizes and used varying
494 methodologies, it remains premature to draw general conclusions about the shape of the
495 relationship between laying order and egg volume in *Parus major*. Nevertheless, non-linear trends
496 involving the first and middle eggs appear to be present across different populations whenever
497 the available data permitted such assessment.

498 When comparing with other species (Tab. 1), the pattern observed in our population resembles
499 that of blue tits, contrasts with that of pied flycatchers, and is the reverse of that reported in more
500 distantly related species such as common eiders, budgerigars, and starlings (Tab.1). In terms of
501 magnitude, our variation is twice that reported for starlings, half that of eiders, and less than one-
502 third that found in pied flycatchers (Tab. 1). Previous studies have addressed non-linearity either
503 by incorporating polynomial terms or by treating laying order as a categorical variable. Our study

504 demonstrated that Generalized Additive Mixed Models (GAMMs) provide a flexible and robust
505 analytical framework to account for non-linearity and temporal autocorrelation in egg-laying
506 sequences.

507 One of the most influential studies on female reproductive strategies in relation to laying order
508 relied on the metric D , the deviation of the last egg from the mean egg volume in a clutch
509 (Slagsvold et al. 1984). While we do not propose GAMMs as a replacement for comparative
510 analyses – given that they cannot account for phylogenetic relatedness – we caution against the
511 continued use of D in future studies based on our results and existing evidence. The choice of D
512 by Slagsvold et al. (1984) was based on preliminary analyses of a single species, the Hooded Crow
513 (*Corvus cornix*), where D was found to be highly correlated with other within-clutch variation
514 measures. However, if our analysis had relied solely on D , we would have detected no evidence
515 of adaptive variation in egg volume since the last egg deviates only ~1% from the mean. Moreover,
516 the widespread presence of non-linear patterns – especially in the early portion of the clutch –
517 reinforces the notion that D cannot adequately capture the complexity of variation in egg volume
518 across laying order. In such cases, D might falsely suggest a similarity between species that
519 display a decrease in later eggs while missing critical variability in middle eggs. Possibly due to
520 the analytical challenges posed by non-linear and temporally structured data, broad-scale
521 comparative analyses on within-clutch egg-size variation – accounting for phylogeny, ecology, and
522 life-history traits – are still lacking. Promising methodological advances, such as those proposed
523 by Rosas-Puchuri et al. (2024), could help overcome these limitations.

524 Finally, while laying order accounted for only 2.88% of the deviance in egg volume, nearly 80% of
525 the variation in egg volume, width, length, and sphericity was attributable to differences between
526 clutches. This strong among-clutch variation is consistent with previous avian studies (reviewed
527 in Christians 2002). Christians (2002) concluded that although females in a population differ
528 widely in their overall capacity to invest in reproduction, each individual tends to maintain
529 relatively stable egg volumes, primarily adjusting investment through clutch size. We found a non-

530 significant linear trend suggesting that eggs were slightly larger in larger clutches – a pattern
531 supported by a significant effect in the same population using a larger sample size (Encabo et al.
532 2001). These results suggest inter-individual differences in investment within the studied
533 population, with some females investing simultaneously in both egg size and clutch size, contrary
534 to classic life-history trade-off expectations.

535 Since egg volume and mass are associated with offspring quality (Slagsvold et al. 1984; Williams
536 1994; Krist 2011), our findings further suggest that female reproductive capacity may be a key
537 target for sexual selection, particularly in monogamous species. Although we did not explicitly
538 account for female quality, our results, combined with previous studies, support the idea that
539 females consistently adjust egg volume, potentially maximizing overall brood success. Future
540 research should explore how factors such as a male phenotype and the reproductive
541 consequences of within- and between-clutch egg size variation influence female reproductive
542 success. Expanding upon the comparative framework established by Slagsvold et al. (1984) will
543 be essential to fully understand reproductive strategies in female birds from a whole-brood
544 perspective.

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Table 1 | Studies found analyzing or reporting egg volume or mass as a function of laying order : Columns Order indicate the taxonomic order of the species, Species gather the common and scientific names of species, Location the country where the study was carried out, N_f the number of females included in the analyses, N_c the number of clutches, N_e the number of eggs, Measure whether mass or volume was used to characterize eggs, Pattern a graphical simplified representation of the patterns of change (“/” indicating increase, “\” decrease, “_” no change), NL the presence “1” or absence “0” of non-linearity in the data, Description a simplified description of the results complementing the two previous columns, Max Diff the difference in the mean predicted measure expressed as a percentage of the mean between the most different egg laying orders, Methodology the method used to test for and asses the existence, magnitude and direction of differences, Covariates those variables used in combination with egg laying order to explain egg mass or volume, Figure the number of the figure in the study displaying the results and Study the names and year of publication of the study containing the information presented in the other columns.

Order	Species	Location	N_f	N_c	N_e	Measure	Pattern	NL	Description	Max diff	Methodology	Covariates	Figure	Study
Anseriformes	Common eiders (<i>Somateria mollissima</i>)	Denmark	812	1099	4531	Volume	\ and /\	1	Pattern depends on clutch size. Small clutches pattern 1, then as clutch size increases, pattern 3 and for biggest clutch sizes pattern 2 with a plateau at the beginning.	Largest clutches 10%	Repeated measures ANOVA	Clutch size, Year, Clutch ID	2	(Christensen and Balsby 2020)
Psittaciformes	Budgerigars (<i>Melopsittacus undulatus</i>)	Laboratory	36	36	211	Mass	/V	1	Second egg is the heaviest, sixth lightest and the others intermediate.	?	GLMM	Female weight, Mate preference, Clutch order, Clutch size, Clutch and Female ID	5A	(Lahaye et al. 2015)
Passeriformes	Spotless starlings (<i>Sturnus unicolor</i>)	Spain	319	647	2885	Volume	\	1	First and second eggs largest then gradual decrease.	2.50%	GLMM with quadratic term	Female ID	2	(Monclús et al. 2017)
Passeriformes	Pied flycatcher (<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i>)	Spain	106	106	594	Volume	V	1	First and last eggs are largest, decrease followed by an increase.	18%	LMM with quadratic term	Female weight, F age, Laying date, Clutch size, Female ID	2	(Fuertes-Recuero et al. 2025)

Order	Species	Location	N _f	N _c	N _e	Measure	Pattern	NL	Description	Max diff	Methodology	Covariates	Figure	Study
Passeriformes	Blue tit (<i>Parus caeruleus</i>)	Sweden	53	53	-	Mass	/_	1	First egg is smallest and later biggest if asynchronously incubated.	4%	Correlation and Paired-sample T-test	-	3	(Nilsson and Svensson 1993)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	Belgium	8	8	47	Mass	_ \	1	First egg is the largest, last smallest, others intermediate.	approx. 75%	LMM (as ANOVA) + Tukey post-hoc	Clutch ID	-	(Lasters et al. 2019)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	Belgium	8	8	47	Volume	_	0	No significant difference.	-	LMM (as ANOVA) + Tukey post-hoc	Clutch ID	5	(Lasters et al. 2019)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	The Netherlands	-	104	741	Mass	V	1	Reported "[egg mass] initially decreased and then increased through the laying sequence".	-	-	-	-	(Lessells et al. 2002)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	Estonia	15	15	30	Volume	_	-	Only first and last eggs compared.	-	Differencing last and first eggs	-	1	(Hörak et al. 2002)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	Estonia	15	15	30	Mass	/	-	Only yolk first and last eggs compared.	-	Differencing last and first eggs	-	1	(Hörak et al. 2002)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	North-eastern China	-	30	337	Volume	/	1	Increase in volume	approx. 5-10%	One-way ANOVA	-	2	(You et al. 2009)
Passeriformes	Great tit (<i>Parus major</i>)	North-eastern China	-	30	337	Mass	/	1	Increase in mass	-	One-way ANOVA +LM	-	2	(You et al. 2009)

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